

predators of eggs of this insect.

N. maeander is found only in Africa. It was first observed by Fennah (1958) in Sudan and French Guinea. Later, Critchley (1977) observed the insect in Ibadan. In Sep 1983 the insect was observed in Badeggi, at a research station of the National Cereal Research Institute.

N. maeander is a potential pest of rice in Africa.

The white fly *Aelurocybotus indicus* David and Subramaniam was found in Senegal, Upper Volta, Nigeria, and Mauritania by Williams and Dips (1981). White fly is an important rice pest in some West African countries. From Feb to Apr

1983, irrigated rice from seedling to maturity at Ibadan was infested. When infestation was high, black sooty mold developed on the leaves, which eventually withered and died. Seriously affected cultivars were TOs 6865, TOs 5827, and TOx 891-212-2-102-1-1. □

Hopperburn caused by whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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WBPH (*Sogatella furcifera* Horvath) population buildup, with 15-35 insects/hill, began the first week of Sep 1983 and reached epidemic levels of 200 to 500

Area and extent of damage by WBPH at different localities in 1983 kharif in the Punjab.

District	Block	Villages affected (no.)	Area infested (ha)	Level of infestation
Patiala	Patiala	7	64	Severe
	Sirhind	29	480	Very severe
	Bhunerheri	5	36	Moderate
	Bassi Pathana	14	172	Severe
	Naba		48	Moderate
Rupar	Chamkaur Sahib	10	200	Very severe
	Total	69	1000	

insects/hill by 20 Sep. About 1,000 ha of rice in the Punjab were hopperburned. PR106 was most seriously damaged, with

10-40% grain yield reduction. Area and level of infestation are given in the table. □

Nomenclature changes for some rice arthropods

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Seed bugs

In a recent review of the seed bug genus *Stollia* Ellenrieder, *Eusarcoris* Hahn became synonymized by *Stollia* (Hsieh et al 1977. A handbook for the determination of the Chinese Hemiptera-Heteroptera). Therefore, the correct names of the species formerly under *Eusarcoris* are

- Stollia capitatus* (Distant)
- Stollia guttiger* (Thunberg)
- Stollia montivagus* (Distant)
- Stollia parvus* (Distant)
- Stollia ventralis* (Westwood)

Mole crickets

The revision of the Afrotropical mole crickets redefined the distribution of *Grylotalpa africana* Palisot de Beauvois. Townsend stated that *G. africana* is confined to Africa and does not occur in Australia or Asia (Townsend, B. C. 1983. A revision of the Afrotropical mole crickets, Bull. Br. Mus. (Nat. Hist.), Entomol. 46(2): 183). *Grylotalpa orientalis* Burmeister now replaces

G. africana in Asia. The correct name for the Asian mole cricket is *Grylotalpa orientalis* Burmeister.

Larval parasites

Mason (1981) reclassified the subfamily Microgastrinae that contains important parasitic genera – *Apanteles* and *Microgaster* – and split *Apanteles* into several new genera. Thereafter, *Apanteles* became synonymized by *Cotesia*. The correct names for the stem borer parasites *A. flavipes* (Cameron) and *A. ruficrus* Haliday are now *Cotesia flavipes* Cameron and *Cotesia ruficrus* (Haliday).

In the same reclassification, *Apanteles schoenobii* Wilkinson became the type of a new genus *Exoryza* Mason and therefore, its valid name is *Exoryza schoenobii* (Wilkinson). Similarly, *Microgaster russatus* Haliday was designated type of *Hygroplitis* Thomson. Its correct name now is *Hygroplitis russatus* (Haliday).

Pupal parasite

Joseph et al (1973) studied the oriental *Brachymeria* and reported that *Brachymeria lasus* (Walker, 1841) and *B. obscurata* (Walker, 1874) were conspecific. *B. lasus* (Walker) was published 33 yr earlier than the latter and is, therefore, the correct name for both species.

Breeding methods for Pipunculidae (Diptera), endoparasites of leafhoppers

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Pipunculid larvae are endoparasites of several Hornoptera families, especially Cicadellidae and Delphacidae, many of which are serious rice pests. We raised *Pipunculus campestris* Ltr., *Eudorylas subterminalis* Collin, and *Tomosvaryella sylvatica* Meig. in captivity at the Zoological Institute, West Berlin.

The breeding box measured 45 × 30 × 20 cm. The lid and two opposing sides were covered with a fine-gauge mesh to facilitate air flow. The two other sides were covered with glass. One glass side could be opened and closed. In the bottom of the box was a round 11-cm-diameter hole through which a potted host plant was inserted (see figure). The box was kept dry and clean to limit fungal infection of the emergent parasitic larvae.

Adult *Euscelis incisus* (Kib.), a species of cicadellid leafhopper (GLH) parasitized by the Pipunculidae species were collected by sweep net during summer and fall 1976 to 1980 from different

Breeding box for Pipunculidae, Berlin, West Germany. 1

places in Berlin. Two other GLH species, *Turrutus socialis* (F1.) and *Mocuellus collinus* (Boh.), also are parasitized.

Twelve- to 15-d-old *Vicia faba* plants were used to feed *E. incisus*. Parasitized hoppers were released on the plants. Pipunculid larvae that emerged successfully pupated in the box. Pupae were transferred to petri dishes containing sterilized sand placed inside the box. To avoid desiccation, sand was moistened with few drops of tap water at 3-d intervals. Emergent flies were fed diluted honey (6 cc water/g honey) on small pieces of blotting paper or cotton to simulate the honeydew secretions of leafhoppers on which the flies naturally live. Blotting paper and cotton were changed every 2 or 3 d.

When the flies had mated, a large number of first- to third-instar nymphs of *E. incisus* were released on the plants for parasitization by Pipunculidae. One such test consisted of 8 flies (4 males + 4 females) and about 150 *E. incisus* nymphs. Sixty-five *E. incisus* were parasitized. Female parasites preferred second- to third-instar nymphs for oviposition.

Parasite larval duration was 29 to 32 d, calculated from the date of oviposition to emergence of larva from the host. Pupal duration was 9 to 21 d. Adult flies lived for 4 to 11 d.

Our studies indicate this breeding method is successful for Pipunculidae that emerge from the first generation of leafhoppers in summer. □

Insecticidal control of the rice yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We evaluated the efficacy of eight emulsifiable concentrate insecticides and a wettable powder for control of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* in a field experiment, in 1983 rabi. Maximum protection—seedling root dip in chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 12 h followed by quinalphos 1.0 kg ai/ha at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DT)—and untreated check treatments were included for comparison. Insecticides were applied 22 and 60 DT.

One application at 22 DT with 0.75 kg ai/ha quinalphos, ethion, triazophos, bromophos, monocrotophos, Mipcin

Efficacy of spray formulation insecticides for control of YSB, Coimbatore, India.^a

Insecticide	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Deadhearts (%)	Whiteheads (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Cypermethrin (Ripcord 10 Ec)	0.10	8.5 bc	7.8 d	2.1 cd
Triazophos (Hostathion 40 Ec)	0.75	3.8 ab	5.7 cd	3.4 b
Bromophos (Nexion 35 Ec)	0.75	4.1 ab	4.1 bc	3.2 bc
Monocrotophos (Monocil 40 Ec)	0.75	4.2 ab	3.3 ab	3.6 b
Ethion (Tafethion 50 Ec)	0.75	3.4 ab	5.5 bc	3.4 b
Quinalphos (Kotophos 25 Ec)	0.75	3.0 a	4.5 bc	3.5 bc
Mipcin 50 WP (MIPC 50 WP)	0.75	4.2 ab	4.5 bc	3.2 bc
UC 54229 99 SP ^b	0.75	4.7 ab	6.1 cd	3.0 cd
RH 0994 45 EC ^b	0.75	5.2 abc	8.2 de	3.3 bc
Maximum protection ^c		1.6 a	2.0 a	4.8 a
Untreated check		11.2 c	11.2 e	2.4 d

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level DMRT.

^b Technical name not available. ^cSeedling root-dip in chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 12 h followed by quinalphos 5G @ 1.0 kg ai/ha at 20, 40, and 60 DT.

(MIPC 50 WP) or UC54229 significantly reduced deadheart damage, and produced results similar to those of maximum protection (see table). Two sprays of mono-

crotophos effectively reduced whiteheads. Monocrotophos 0.75 kg ai/ha most effectively reduced YSB infestation at tillering and flowering. □

Toxicity of insecticides to the predatory mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter

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The mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* is an effective predator of rice hopper eggs and nymphs. We assessed the toxicity to the mirid bug of some commonly used rice insecticides. With an atomizer, potted 45-d-old TN1 rice plants were sprayed

Toxicity of insecticides to the mirid bug *C. lividipennis*, Coimbatore, India.

Insecticide	Formulation (%)	Corrected mortality (% T. V.) ^a at indicated time after spraying		
		1 d	3 d	5 d
Endosulfan	0.07	34.72 a	7.40 a	20.63 a
Neem oil	5	36.90 a	38.11 bcd	20.01 a
Carbaryl (50% WP)	1.0	49.59 a	81.99 e	46.02 a
Phosalone	0.07	62.15 abc	46.36 bcde	36.07 a
Monocrotophos	0.08	65.67 abc	60.85 de	53.96 a
Chlorpyrifos	0.04	83.51 bc	60.58 de	33.25 a
Quinalphos	0.075	90.00 c	50.08 cde	41.85 a

^a In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at P = 0.005, T. V. = Arc Sin√percentage transformed value.